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**ACTIVITIES OF NON-STATE PENSION FUNDS IN RUSSIA:
PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS**

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The development of non-state pension funds (NPFs) in Russia is a key element in building a balanced pension system that reduces the burden on the state budget and increases the income level of future retirees. However, its potential has not been fully developed today, which led to the purpose of this article — to analyze the problems and prospects of non-governmental pension funds.

The article presents an analysis of the legal definition and key characteristics of non-governmental pension funds in accordance with Russian legislation, which include the socio-economic sphere of activity, functions (financial, insurance, investment, social), goals and objectives of activities, sources of financing, as well as the organizational and legal form. Special attention is paid to changing the status of NPFs from non-profit organizations to joint-stock companies. The advantages of corporatization of NPFs, such as expanded access to capital, increased financial transparency, effective corporate control and an objective market assessment, are emphasized. The NPF's corporate governance system, which includes senior, executive and internal control bodies and is aimed at ensuring financial stability and protecting the rights of depositors and participants, is also being considered.

The article considers a multi-level system of interacting organizations that ensure the operation of non-governmental pension funds in Russia, which includes professional participants (actuaries, depositories, management companies and auditors), government regulators, as well as the final recipients of services — legal entities and individuals who are depositors and participants in the system of additional pension provision. The functions of individual participants in the non-state pension provision market are listed.

Corporate (professional, industry-specific), territorial and private (individual) NPFs are investigated, the features of their functioning are revealed, and the main results of the activities of the most prominent representatives of the market are considered.

It is determined that over the past decade, the Russian market of non-governmental pension funds has undergone a radical transformation, resulting in a reduction in the number of participants from more than a hundred to less than forty. The main reasons were the tightening of state regulation (increased capital requirements, the introduction of a guarantee system), the «freezing» of funded pensions (2014-2023), which undermined the business model of funds, as well as the loss of public confidence. The result was a high concentration of the market around large players with state participation and a transition from quantitative growth to qualitative development in conditions of increased reliability, but also less diversity. The key modern task remains to restore the trust of citizens and stimulate voluntary pension savings.

The article analyzes the key challenges facing non-state pension funds (NPFs) in Russia: crisis of trust and passivity of citizens caused by past scandals and the complexity of the system; the difficulty of long-term investment in conditions of high inflation, conservative strategies and macroeconomic volatility; demographic pressure and changing employment patterns; strict government regulation, which, while increasing reliability, simultaneously inhibits innovation and growth; digital transformation, which carries cybersecurity risks and creates a «digital divide» for the older generation. It is concluded that modern NPFs operate in a complex paradigm, having to balance reliability, profitability and adaptation to new economic and technological realities.

Keywords: non-governmental pension funds, pension provision, pension system of Russia, pension savings, financial markets, public confidence, financial literacy, Bank of Russia.

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SPISOK LITERATURY

1. Bal'zhirov, C. B. Negosudarstvennye pensionnye fondy v Rossii: preimushchestva i riski dlya investorov, perspektivy razvitiya / C. B. Bal'zhirov // *Ekonomika i biznes: teoriya i praktika*. — 2024. — 2-1(108). — S. 19–23. — DOI 10.24412/2411-0450-2024-2-19-23. — EDNAZUKDZ.
2. Bitkina, I. K. K voprosu o razvitiu normativnykh osnov obespecheniya finansovoy ustojchivosti sistemy strahovaniya vkladov i pensionnykh nakoplenij v Rossijskoj Federacii / I. K. Bitkina // *Sibirskaya finansovaya shkola*. — 2023. — 3(151). — S. 131–136. — DOI 10.34020/1993-4386-2023-3-131-136. — EDN FEWCIT.
3. Vysochina, M. V. Metodicheskie podhody k ocenke finansovoy gramotnosti naseleniya / M. V. Vysochina, N. A. Fokina // *Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii*. — 2025. — 1(70). — S. 56–71. — DOI 10.29039/2312-5330-2025-1-56-71. — EDN JWUVAV.
4. Gordienko, M. S. Analiz effektivnosti negosudarstvennogo pensionnogo fonda / M. S. Gordienko, M. E. Zhadyaeva, A. A. Aliev. — Moskva-Berlin : Moskva-Berlin, 2021. — 88 s. — ISBN 978-5-4499-1955-7. — EDN LCVVEE.
5. Gorlovskaya, I. G. Razvitie rynka pensionnykh nakoplenij: povedencheskij aspekt pokoleniya Z / I. G. Gorlovskaya, I. M. Reutova // *Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii*. — 2021. — 2(55). — S. 103–110. — DOI 10.37279/2312-5330-2021-2-103-110. — EDN XBUIEE.
6. Gorovec, N. A. Tendencii razvitiya negosudarstvennykh pensionnykh fondov v Rossii / N. A. Gorovec // *Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii*. — 2018. — 1(42). — S. 48–56. — EDN XUMZHV.
7. Danilova, E. G. Sushchnost' i znachenie negosudarstvennykh pensionnykh fondov / E. G. Danilova // *Novyj universitet. Seriya: Ekonomika i pravo*. — 2011. — 4(4). — S. 95–96. — EDN SNJMCP.
8. Deyatel'nost' NPF po NPO i PDS v 2024 godu. Monitoring otdel'nykh pokazatelej / Komitet po pensionnym i sberegatel'nym produktam NAPF. — URL: napf.ru/upload/iblock/d24/jiitor3lerm56cbgwp8edzd4ekms78ml/ (data obrashcheniya: 26.08.2025).
9. Krylova, E. R. Negosudarstvennye pensionnye fondy: problemy i perspektivy razvitiya / E. R. Krylova, I. V. Kurnikova // *Mnogourovnevnoe obshchestvennoe vosproizvodstvo: voprosy teorii i praktiki*. — 2017. — 13(29). — S. 60–65. — EDN YMCHTH.
10. Kulikova, E. I. Doveritel'noe upravlenie finansovymi aktivami / E. I. Kulikova, N. M. Rebel'skij ; *Finansovyj universitet pri Pravitel'stve Rossijskoj Federacii*. — Moskva : Prometej, 2023. — 300 s. — URL: biblioclub.ru/index.php?page=book&id=721416 (data obrashcheniya: 21.08.2025).
11. «NPF Blagosostoyanie» — negosudarstvennyj pensionnyj fond // Oficial'nyj sajt AO «NPF Blagosostoyanie». — URL: npfb.ru/o-fonde/ (data obrashcheniya: 26.08.2025).
12. Osnovnye pokazateli deyatel'nosti negosudarstvennykh pensionnykh fondov // Oficial'nyj sajt Banka Rossii. — URL: cbr.ru/finmarket/supervision/sv_coll/ops_npf/2024/ (data obrashcheniya: 26.08.2025).
13. Pokazateli deyatel'nosti AO «NPF «BLAGOSOSTOYANIE» // Oficial'nyj sajt AO «Blagosostoyanie». — URL: npfb.ru/o-fonde/raskrytie-informatsii/ (data obrashcheniya: 26.08.2025).
14. Pokazateli deyatel'nosti AO «Hanty-Mansijskij NPF» // Oficial'nyj sajt AO «Hanty-Mansijskij NPF». — URL: www.hmnpf.ru/about/disclosures/performance-indicators/ (data obrashcheniya: 25.08.2025).
15. Sovremennaya transformaciya pensionnoj sistemy i formirovanie «dlinnykh deneg» v rossijskoj ekonomike / E. I. Kulikova, L. N. Andrianova, I. A. Guseva [i dr.]. — Moskva : Obshchestvo s ogranichennoj otvetstvennost'yu «Izdatel'stvo «KnoRus», 2022. — 190 s. — ISBN 978-5-406-10441-5. — EDN DJHUHB.
16. Tarasova, O. V. Deyatel'nost' negosudarstvennykh pensionnykh fondov Rossii: problemy i perspektivy / O. V. Tarasova // *Nauka i obrazovanie transportu*. — 2016. — 1. — S. 191–195. — EDN XEPEXP.
17. Tereshchenko, T. A. Perspektivy realizacii social'noj politiki Rossii posredstvom negosudarstvennykh pensionnykh fondov / T. A. Tereshchenko, I. V. Balashova // *Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii*. — 2023. — 1(62). — S. 82–94. — EDN EEREGO.
18. O negosudarstvennykh pensionnykh fondah: Federal'nyj zakon ot 07.05.1998 N 75-FZ (red. ot 31.07.2025). — URL: www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_18626/2e073b16fe21d3804e163f8392924667479573e6/ (data obrashcheniya: 21.08.2025).
19. Yakovenko, N. A. Negosudarstvennye pensionnye fondy: perspektivy razvitiya v Rossii / N. A. Yakovenko // *Pravo i praktika*. — 2022. — 1. — S. 191–196. — DOI 10.24412/2411-2275-2022-1-191-196. — EDN RTLJDC.
20. Yarovaya, E. S. Razvitie sistemy negosudarstvennykh pensionnykh fondov na osnove novykh tekhnologij v finansovom sektore : dissertaciya na soiskanie uchenoj stepeni kandidata ekonomicheskikh nauk / Yarovaya Ekaterina Sergeevna, 2023. — 189 s. — EDN DSHFMZ.

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